
ADVANCED PEDAGOGICAL IN IMPROVING THE QUALITY OF EDUCATION THE SIGNIFICANCE OF EXPERIENCES IN THE EDUCATIONAL SYSTEM

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Annotation. If the tasks of reforming the education system and improving its quality are successfully solved, social and political spheres will slowly change, democratic values will settle in people's minds, and a person will consciously determine his place in society. Improving the quality of education and problems are presented.

Key words: Education system, quality of education, Education, Pedagogical activities, Knowledge, skills and qualifications.

Introduction. Public education is a priority of social policy in Uzbekistan one of the directions. It is the quality and convenience of school education that belongs to the state ground for training highly qualified personnel, reflecting development prospects creates. To the opinion that it is impossible to save funds for education we have no choice but to join [1, B. 2]. In the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan it is not for nothing that it is emphasized that school affairs are under the control of the state. A. Abdulla Avloni as said "Education for us is life - or death, or salvation - or destruction, or happiness."- or it's a matter of disaster."

Because the development and future of Uzbekistan is in the hands of these young people, i.e. modern personnel, the total attention is on their free-thinking, world getting an education that meets the educational standards for a great future is a

solid foundation being laid. For this, first of all, the quality of education should be increased according to world standards. Modern education it imposes a great responsibility on each person. Because education the process of all-round development of a person, high-minded, nationally proud, in view of the goal of raising a well-educated, spiritually and physically mature person holds and directs its actions from this point of view[3, B. 4].

From the first steps of independence, education of the young generation is part of life should find its place and be subordinated to the tasks of building a democratic state it was reported. Years later, modern innovative education is different possibilities of implementation in methods are expanding day by day. In all this, all the responsibility rests with the teacher Self-management is required from the learner without being burdened.

There is a new approach to education, improving the quality of education reform of educational programs in accordance with modern requirements and the young generation It is possible to solve the problems of education in a reasonable way in the implementation of great intentions, first of all, the education system up to school age training of highly qualified specialists, starting with the education of children forming the essence of high intelligence, for this modern material technology and it is necessary to reform all areas up to the creation of the information base.

The tasks of reforming the education system and improving its quality have been successful if it is solved, the social and political spheres will change slowly, democratic in people's minds values are decided, a person consciously determines his place in society. The root of the changes happening in our lives today its essence lies directly in the educational process. In the field of education The main directions of the ongoing fundamental reforms are as follows:

- reforming the system of educational content;
- reforming the educational system;
- reforming the mechanism of education based on the market economy;
- a new approach to the educational process of parents, teachers and students formation of views;

- it consists of putting new pedagogical technologies into practice.
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Expanding and deepening the content of education and its content the content includes not only knowledge, skills, qualifications, but also universal human culture the experience of creative activity, environment - the idea of including relationships in the environment very important. Advanced pedagogic, social experiences and pedagogic skills is an important factor in formation. The main aspect of new pedagogical technologies it is necessary to reorganize school textbooks at a high level. The creation of textbooks is based on many years of scientific, cultural, aesthetic and spiritual experiences should be carried out [4, B. 3].

Pedagogical activity in the educational process has a creative character according to its own work have It is known that creativity is needed only when a person faces a problem. Teaching activity has such characteristics.

Conclusion

Pedagogical The main essence of creativity is the purpose and character of pedagogical activity sure Pedagogical activity is a person's personality, his worldview, beliefs, consciousness, it is the process of solving countless pedagogical issues subordinated to the character.

The creativity of the teacher is in the ways of solving these problems it is expressed in the ability to find solutions. Pedagogical creativity its source is advanced pedagogical experience. Advanced pedagogical experience is problematic is very rich in situations. By advanced pedagogical experience, we mean the teacher himself creative approach to the pedagogical task, new in the education of students, we understand that they are looking for modern, effective ways and means.

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